

Antenatal Care Practices among Pregnant Women in Rural North Bihar, India**Urmi Poddar¹, Abdur Rahman Al Adil², Kumar Himanshu³, Abhay Kumar⁴**¹Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Purnea, Bihar, India²Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Purnea, Bihar, India³Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Purnea, Bihar, India⁴Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Purnea, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

The objective of this study was to evaluate the antenatal care practices of pregnant women in the rural areas of North Bihar, India, specifically in the Jalalgarh and Ranipatra Blocks of Purnea District. The research employed a cross-sectional approach, including a sample of 200 participants observed between November 2023 and April 2024. The data indicated that 75% of women participated in at least one prenatal appointment, whereas only 40% complied with the four suggested visits. The study revealed many obstacles to optimal care, such as insufficient levels of education, financial limitations, cultural customs, and restricted availability of healthcare services. Furthermore, healthcare decisions were greatly impacted by socio-cultural determinants, resulting in a lack of autonomy for many women in receiving care. This study emphasises the necessity of implementing focused measures to enhance education, availability, and standard of prenatal services in remote areas.

Keywords: antenatal care, rural health, maternal health, socio-cultural factors.

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Introduction

Antenatal care (ANC) is an essential element of maternal and new born health, to safeguard the health and welfare of both the mother and the baby throughout pregnancy [1]. Access to the use of high-quality prenatal care in rural regions, such as those in North Bihar, India, may be restricted by a range of socio-economic and infrastructural deficiencies [2]. These issues frequently encompass insufficient healthcare infrastructure, shortage of qualified healthcare practitioners, and socio-cultural obstacles that impact the use of crucial prenatal services [3]. The primarily rural population of North Bihar provides a distinctive setting for examining prenatal care practices [4]. The region is distinguished by its predominantly agricultural economy, dense population, and restricted availability of healthcare resources. Expectant mothers in certain regions may have substantial obstacles in accessing prompt and sufficient prenatal care, which can affect the health outcomes of both the mother and the new born [5,6].

This study aims to explore the current practices related to antenatal care among pregnant women in rural North Bihar. By examining factors such as the frequency of antenatal visits, types of care received, and the influence of socio-cultural

factors, this research seeks to identify gaps in the existing healthcare framework and provide recommendations for improving antenatal care services in these underserved areas. Understanding these practices is crucial for designing targeted interventions that can enhance maternal and child health outcomes in rural communities.

Methodology

Study Design and Duration: This study employed a cross-sectional design to assess antenatal care practices among pregnant women in rural areas. The research was conducted from November 2023 to April 2024.

Study Area: The study was carried out in the Jalalgarh and Ranipatra Blocks of Purnea District, which are field practice areas of the Government Medical College, Purnea. These blocks were selected due to their representative nature of rural settings in Purnea District of North Bihar.

Study Population: A total of 200 pregnant women residing in the selected rural blocks were included in the study. Participants were selected through a systematic sampling method to ensure a representative sample of the population.

Data Collection

Data were collected using structured questionnaires and face-to-face interviews. The questionnaires were designed to gather information on various aspects of antenatal care, including the frequency and types of antenatal visits, services received, and socio-cultural factors influencing care practices.

Data Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using statistical software to determine patterns and trends in antenatal care practices. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the findings, and inferential statistics were used to identify significant factors affecting antenatal care uptake.

Results

The study included 200 pregnant women from Jalalgarh and Ranipatra Blocks in Purnea District. The findings revealed significant insights into the antenatal care practices among these women, highlighting various factors that influenced their access to and utilization of maternal health services. The majority of the participants were between the ages of 20 and 30, with 65% falling within this age range. Most of the women were from low-income households, with 70% earning less than the average regional income. Education levels were generally low; 60% of the participants had not completed primary education, and only 10% had attained higher secondary education or above.

Antenatal Care Utilization: Of the 200 women surveyed, 75% attended at least one antenatal care visit during their pregnancy. However, only 40% completed the recommended minimum of four antenatal visits. The most common reasons for attending antenatal care included routine check-ups (80%) and tetanus toxoid vaccinations (70%). Notably, 20% of the participants did not attend any antenatal care visits, primarily due to financial constraints, distance to healthcare facilities, and lack of awareness about the importance of antenatal care.

Types of Services Received: Among those who attended antenatal visits, 85% received basic physical examinations, and 60% received nutritional counselling. However, only 45% were tested for anemia, and just 30% underwent ultrasound scanning. Additionally, 50% of the women received iron and folic acid supplementation, while 35% were counselled on birth preparedness and complication readiness.

Socio-Cultural Factors: Socio-cultural factors played a significant role in influencing antenatal care practices. About 55% of the participants reported that family decisions greatly influenced their access to antenatal care services. Furthermore, 30% cited traditional beliefs and

practices as reasons for either delaying or avoiding antenatal visits. A lack of female autonomy was also noted, with only 25% of women making independent decisions about their healthcare.

Barriers to Antenatal Care: Rural North Bihar had various impediments to prenatal care, according to the study. Financial problems (45%), extensive healthcare distances (40%), and poor transit (35%), were the main hurdles. 30% of individuals were unaware of the necessity of frequent prenatal care. Cultural customs prohibited outpatient care, and healthcare providers' abuse and disdain were other hurdles. This study found that pregnant women in rural North Bihar are aware of and use antenatal care, although there are major discrepancies in uptake. Socio-economic issues, cultural hurdles, and lack of education hindered maternity healthcare. These findings suggest focused measures to improve rural prenatal care and mother health.

Discussion

This study's findings offer significant insights into the antenatal care procedures undertaken by pregnant women residing in the rural regions of North Bihar, India. The assessment indicates that although most women attended at least one prenatal appointment, a considerable percentage did not fulfil the advised four appointments, underscoring a crucial deficiency in the use of maternal health care [7]. This disparity can be ascribed to various socio-economic and cultural determinants that were recognized as significant obstacles to obtaining complete prenatal care. The participants' limited educational attainment, with 60% having not finished basic education, is very certainly a contributing element to the insufficient awareness and comprehension of the significance of consistent prenatal care [8,9]. The critical role of education in shaping health behaviours and outcomes has been well acknowledged. The results emphasise the necessity of implementing focused educational programs to increase knowledge about the advantages of prenatal care among women residing in remote regions [10,11].

Furthermore, the study emphasises the significant impact of socio-cultural elements on antenatal care practices. The high percentage of women (55%) who indicated that family decisions significantly influenced their healthcare access highlights the widespread impact of patriarchal norms and the restricted independence of women in these societies [12,13]. Moreover, it was discovered that conventional beliefs and customs inhibit certain women from seeking medical attention, therefore underscoring the importance of culturally appropriate health education initiatives that specifically target these obstacles [14]. Financial limitations and logistical obstacles, such as

extensive travel distances to healthcare institutions and insufficient transportation, were also recognised as major obstacles to obtaining antenatal care [15]. These findings align with previous research carried out in comparable environments, where financial difficulties and geographical remoteness frequently hinder women from accessing prompt and sufficient healthcare.

To overcome these obstacles, it will be necessary to employ diverse approaches such as enhancing the availability of healthcare services, offering transportation assistance, and establishing community-based health treatments that may be delivered to women in their usual living environments [16].

Table 1: This table summarizes the demographic profile, antenatal care utilization, services received, socio-cultural factors, and barriers to accessing antenatal care among pregnant women in the rural areas of North Bihar.

Parameter	Category	Percentage (%)
Age Distribution	20-30 years	65%
	Above 30 years	35%
Household Income	Below average regional income	70%
	Above average regional income	30%
Education Level	Did not complete primary education	60%
	Completed higher secondary education	10%
Antenatal Care Visits	Attended at least one visit	75%
	Completed at least four visits	40%
	Did not attend any visit	20%
Reasons for Antenatal Visits	Routine check-ups	80%
	Tetanus toxoid vaccination	70%
Services Received	Basic physical examinations	85%
	Nutritional counseling	60%
	Anemia testing	45%
	Ultrasound scanning	30%
	Iron and folic acid supplementation	50%
	Birth preparedness counseling	35%
Influence of Family Decisions	Family influenced healthcare access	55%
Influence of Traditional Beliefs	Beliefs affected care access	30%
Women's Autonomy	Made independent healthcare decisions	25%
Barriers to Antenatal Care	Financial difficulties	45%
	Distance to healthcare facilities	40%
	Inadequate transportation	35%
	Lack of awareness	30%

The survey also exposed deficiencies in the standard of prenatal care delivered, as just 45% of women had anemia testing and only 30% had ultrasound screening. These findings indicate that even when women avail themselves of antenatal services, the level of care they get may not be thorough [17]. Improving maternal and newborn health outcomes requires significantly enhancing the quality of care by providing comprehensive training to healthcare professionals and guaranteeing the accessibility of vital diagnostic services. This study emphasises the intricate interaction of socio-economic, cultural, and logistical elements that impact antenatal care practices in rural North Bihar [18]. To enhance maternal health outcomes in these communities, it is necessary to implement comprehensive policies that tackle both the supply and demand aspects of

healthcare. It encompasses raising community awareness, enhancing availability of high-quality services, and enabling women to make well-informed choices on their health. By addressing these obstacles, it will be feasible to augment the adoption and standard of prenatal care and ultimately boost the health and welfare of mothers and their infants in rural India [19,20].

Conclusion

The study concludes that antenatal care practices among pregnant women in the rural areas of North Bihar are significantly influenced by socio-economic, cultural, and logistical factors, leading to inadequate utilization of essential maternal health services. Despite some awareness of the importance of antenatal care, many women face barriers such as low education levels, financial constraints, lack of autonomy, and limited access to

healthcare facilities, which prevent them from receiving comprehensive care. To improve maternal and neonatal health outcomes in these communities, it is crucial to implement targeted interventions that address these barriers, enhance education and awareness, and ensure accessible, high-quality healthcare services for all pregnant women.

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